

Training Area Summaries

This document presents the results of a systematic mapping exercise conducted within the Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks (PATTERN) project to identify, characterise, and analyse existing training resources relevant to Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI) across Europe (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094416>).

The training area summaries were produced as an outcome of Task 1.1 (Mapping and analysis of training activities) within Work Package 1 (WP1), led by Aarhus University, of the PATTERN project. The work was carried out by the following consortium members: Aarhus University, European Science Foundation, Sissa – International School for Advanced Studies, Learning Planet Institute, OpenAIRE, European Association of Research Managers and Administrators, Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele, DANS - Data Archiving and Networked Services, Ruđer Bošković Institute, SciLink, and Universidade do Minho.

The summaries provide a structured overview of the landscape of Open RRI training resources and constitute a core component of the state-of-the-art mapping undertaken in WP1. They informed the subsequent quality assessment of training provision conducted in Task 1.3, the results of which are reported in Deliverable 1.1, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10640916>.

The document compiles structured information for multiple Open RRI training areas, including Open Access, FAIR data and Research Data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results, Science Communication, Management and Leadership, as well as selected cross-cutting Open Science and general RRI resources. For each area, it details the types of resources identified, target audiences, expertise levels, delivery modes, content themes, languages, access conditions, and qualifications, alongside an analysis of coverage, gaps, limitations, and reuse potential.

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Open Access

Summary

Open Access (OA) is a well-established concept within the research ecosystem and refers to efforts to make scientific publications—particularly peer-reviewed journal articles—freely accessible to readers. While the underlying idea of openly sharing scholarly knowledge predates the digital era, contemporary Open Access initiatives primarily focus on digital publications made available via the internet. The OA movement has been shaped and strengthened by a series of key declarations and initiatives, most notably the Budapest Open Access Initiative, which provided an early and influential articulation of its principles.

Despite its maturity, Open Access remains subject to diverse interpretations and implementation pathways, reflecting the existence of multiple OA routes. The motivation and capacity to publish research outputs in Open Access formats also vary considerably across research disciplines, geographical regions, policy environments, and funding mandates. Achieving a globally harmonised approach to Open Access therefore remains challenging, although progress has been made through the alignment of regional and institutional policies. A prominent example is Plan S and its ten principles, which came into force in 2021 and brought together a coalition of major funding organisations. Nevertheless, the reach of Plan S—via cOAlition S—is still limited in global terms, and broader international uptake remains necessary to achieve comprehensive coverage.

Within the framework of Open Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI), Open Access is a core component. From an ethical standpoint, publicly funded research should be openly available to society, enabling transparency, reuse, and broader societal benefit. Open Access also serves as a foundation for other key dimensions of Open RRI that underpin the objectives of the PATTERN project, including Open Science practices, FAIR data principles, and Citizen Science. In this context, training for the diverse stakeholder groups involved in research is essential—not only to raise awareness of the importance of Open Access, but also to support the wider cultural change required to embed openness and responsibility across research systems.

Resources and content themes

A total of sixteen training resources and eighteen non-course resources were identified, covering most delivery modalities, with the exception of blended learning, which was not represented. The vast majority of resources (28) target beginner-level learners, while only a small number are aimed at intermediate level (3) and none explicitly address advanced learners. A limited subset (3 resources) was identified as being suitable for all expertise levels.

With respect to target audiences, the distribution is similarly skewed towards broad categories, with most resources addressing either all audiences (14) or all researchers/academics (8). More specifically targeted resources are fewer and mainly

focus on students (4) and doctoral/PhD candidates (5), with only two resources explicitly designed for trainers.

A further bias towards generalisation is evident in the scientific domain coverage, with the majority of resources classified as generic (28). Only a small number of domain-specific resources were identified, namely those addressing the social sciences (2) and medical sciences (1). The primary language of delivery is overwhelmingly English (28 resources), although a limited number of resources are available in French (3), Croatian (2), and Italian (1).

Regarding pedagogical features, twenty resources specify learning outcomes, while fourteen do not. In terms of formal recognition, the majority of resources (24) do not provide any form of qualification. Where qualifications are offered, these most commonly take the form of digital badges (7), with only a single resource contributing to ECTS credits.

Table 1 Open Access resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (10), in-person (6)	Static resource (9), webinar / lecture (9)
Expertise level	Beginner (14), Intermediate (2), Advanced (0), All (0)	Beginner (14), Intermediate (1), Advanced (0), All (3)
Main audience	All audiences (10), All researchers / academics (1), Students (3), Doctoral / PhD students (2), General public (0), Research support (0), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (0), Other (0)	All audiences (4), All researchers / academics (7), Students (1), Doctoral / PhD students (3), General public (0), Research support (0), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (2), Other (0)
Learning outcomes	Specified (12), non-specified (6)	Specified (8), non-specified (10)
Scientific domain	Generic (13), Natural Sciences (0), Engineering & Technology (0), Medical & Health Sciences (1), Social Sciences and Humanities (2)	Generic (15), Natural Sciences (0), Engineering & Technology (0), Medical & Health Sciences (0), Social Sciences and Humanities (0)
Primary language	Croatian (1), English (12), French (3), Greek (1), Hungarian (1), Swedish (1)	English (16), Croatian (1), Italian (1)
Qualification	Badge (7), Certification (0), Accreditation (0), ECTS (1), Other (0), None (8)	None (16)

The range of topics addressed by Open Access learning resources is relatively broad, with good coverage across many thematic areas. In total, ten content topics were identified. As expected, “Open Access” itself is by far the most prominent theme, accounting for the largest number of resources (28). The next most frequently addressed topics are scholarly publishing (9), followed by the publishing lifecycle (6) and rights retention strategies (6). A comparable level of coverage is observed for copyright (5) and preprint servers (5).

In contrast, several topics are notably underrepresented, particularly predatory publishing (4), repositories (2), and funder requirements (1). These areas therefore constitute clear gaps in the current training landscape, with funder requirements emerging as a priority topic for further development. More generally, aside from Open Access as a core concept, most other thematic areas are addressed at relatively low levels, despite being integral components of effective Open Access practice.

Additional gaps may also exist in training that addresses specific Open Access routes (such as gold, diamond, or other models), as well as in relation to regional, European Commission, and programme-specific funding frameworks, where requirements and expectations often vary substantially across policy and institutional contexts. Finally, given its central role in shaping the contemporary Open Access policy environment, Plan S represents a critical area that would benefit from more explicit and systematic coverage within Open Access training resources.

Table 2 Open Access content themes

Content theme	Number of training activities
Open Access	62
Funder requirements	50
Rights retention strategy	40
Repository	39
Copyright	28
Publishing lifecycle	28
Preprint servers	25
Scholarly publishing	23
Predatory publishing	22
Research evaluation	21

Limitations of the current Open Access training landscape

Open Access as a concept is widely recognised within the Open Science community, at least at a foundational level; however, the coverage of formal training and learning resources identified through this mapping remains comparatively limited. A substantial body of relevant material exists outside what is traditionally classified as “training” and may therefore have been omitted from the analysis. These resources could nevertheless merit further investigation to assess their suitability for reuse or adaptation.

One prominent example is the annual Open Access Week, which is a well-established global initiative and provides a valuable focal point for community engagement around Open Access. Similarly, a range of independently produced guides and toolkits, such as those developed by organisations like Jisc, offer substantial practical information. Although such resources often address broader Open Science topics in addition to Open Access, they represent important opportunities for awareness raising and capacity building that could be leveraged within an Open RRI context.

An additional challenge lies in the rapidly evolving nature of the Open Access policy landscape. New mandates and policy frameworks continue to emerge as Open Access gains wider acceptance, particularly in regions where openness has previously been limited due to concerns around data sharing, costs, or intellectual property. This dynamic environment complicates efforts to ensure that training and learning resources remain accurate and up to date.

A further issue concerns the classification of expertise levels. Most mapped resources are labelled as “beginner”, raising questions about how beginner, intermediate, advanced, and “all-level” categories are defined and differentiated. This suggests a potential need to develop more progressive learning pathways for individuals who are already familiar with basic Open Access principles and require more advanced or specialised training.

Resources meriting further in-depth quality analysis

Among the mapped resources, those developed through the FOSTER and FIT4RRI projects stand out as strong candidates for more detailed quality assessment. These initiatives produced extensive and well-structured learning materials that were highly relevant at the time of their release. Although some of this content is now partially outdated—having been developed prior to key policy developments such as Plan S—there are ongoing efforts to update and republish these resources.

As both initiatives are overseen by OpenAIRE, they represent strategically valuable assets that can be closely monitored, selectively adapted, and potentially aligned with PATTERN’s objectives and training formats.

Strategic engagement for advancing Open Access training

To further advance the goals of Open Access, it may be beneficial for PATTERN to engage more directly with cOAlition S and its partners, as well as with publishers and other key stakeholders in the scholarly communication ecosystem. Involving these actors in the co-creation of learning and training resources could support the development of authoritative, up-to-date content while also increasing stakeholder buy-in. Such collaboration would not only strengthen OA training provision but could also enhance the visibility and impact of PATTERN’s work within the wider research and policy landscape.

FAIR Data and Research Data Management

Summary

In an era characterised by the rapid growth and increasing complexity of research data, effective management of data in accordance with the FAIR principles—that is, ensuring data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—is a cornerstone of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). First articulated in 2016, the FAIR principles emphasise not only the readability and usability of data by humans, but also—crucially—their machine-readability. Given the scale and volume of contemporary research data, machine-actionable data are essential to enable researchers to cope with data abundance and to meaningfully build upon, integrate, and collaborate with the work of others.

The FAIR principles highlight, among other aspects, the importance of rich metadata and globally unique and persistent identifiers to support findability; the use of open, free, and universally implementable protocols to ensure accessibility; the adoption of shared and FAIR-aligned vocabularies to enable interoperability; and the application of clear and explicit licences to facilitate reuse. Since their publication, the FAIR principles have gained broad international acceptance, although their practical implementation remains uneven and, in many cases, ongoing.

At European level, the importance of FAIR data management has been explicitly recognised within the European Commission’s vision of “Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World”, which also clearly distinguishes between the concepts of open and FAIR. Within Horizon Europe, the European Union’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation in force since 2021, researchers are required to make research data “as FAIR as possible, as open as necessary”. The FAIR principles also constitute one of the six guiding principles of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

In this context, it is evident that training researchers in FAIR research data management is essential. While FAIR compliance is increasingly driven by top-down requirements from the European Commission and other research funders, it is also being progressively embraced by researchers themselves. The application of FAIR principles is widely recognised as supporting responsible, transparent, and accessible research practices, ultimately enhancing the quality, reproducibility, and societal value of research.

Mapped resources

Table 3 summarises the results of the mapping exercise for FAIR data and Research Data Management (RDM) training. A comparable number of resources were identified for FAIR data (31) and RDM (33). Most resources are generic in scope, with a smaller subset focusing on specific disciplinary contexts. The majority consist of static materials, including recorded webinars, videos, documents, and websites. Although these are typically not designed as standalone courses, they are valuable as

supplementary learning resources, for instance as components of training programmes or as further reading supporting teaching and self-directed learning.

In addition, seven FAIR-specific and ten RDM-specific course-type training activities were identified. These structured offerings are particularly relevant for informing the development of PATTERN training activities. Where expertise levels were specified, resources were predominantly aimed at beginners or designed for all levels, facilitating adaptation and reuse. This reflects a characteristic of FAIR and RDM training, where progression often involves expanding topical coverage or developing greater depth rather than increasing difficulty.

The vast majority of resources are provided in English. This partly reflects English as the working language of the PATTERN project and of the mapping contributors, as well as the dominance of international and European collaborative initiatives, which typically disseminate training materials in English.

Table 3 FAIR Data and Research Data Management (RDM) resources

	FAIR	RDM
Number of training resources (e-learning, courses, workshops)	7	10
Number of non-course resources (static resources, webinar recordings)	24	23
Expertise level	5 Beginner, 9 All (rest not specified)	9 Beginner, 5 All (rest not specified)
Main audience	Primarily “all audiences”/ “all researchers and academics” (22/28)	Primarily “all audiences”/ “all researchers and academics” (11/15)
Number of trainings with specified learning outcomes	4	9
Scientific domain	1 Engineering, 1 Natural Science, 3 Medical Science, 23 generic	2 Social Sciences, 31 generic
Primary language	2 Italian, 1 French, 28 English	3 Croatian, 1 Greek, 1 Hungarian, 28 English (1 English resource also available in Dutch)

Content themes

Tables 4 and 5 summarise the training areas and topics for which resources are available, highlighting differences in the extent of coverage across themes. At the time of data collection, FAIR data and RDM were analysed using the same set of content

themes, as the two areas were not initially treated as separate categories. During the subsequent analysis, however, it became clear that although FAIR data and RDM are closely related and complementary, they represent distinct topics. This distinction is reflected in the differentiated content themes used for each area.

Table 4 FAIR data content themes

Content themes	Number of resources
FAIR	25
Data management	17
Data sharing	6
Data reuse	5
Data archiving	5
Data discovery	0
Quality assessment	0
Ethics	5
Open data	6
Open access	1
Open science	7

Table 5 Research Data Management content themes

Content themes	Number of resources
FAIR	6
Data management	12
Data sharing	7
Data reuse	6
Data archiving	10
Data discovery	4
Quality assessment	4
Ethics	7
Open data	7
Open access	4
Open science	6

At first glance, all identified topics are covered by one or more of the collected resources, with a substantial number of resources addressing FAIR data, data management, and data archiving (each covered by more than ten resources). However, the current set of content themes proved to be too generic to serve as an adequate basis for curriculum development. To address this, the content themes were rephrased and expanded, and further differentiated by expertise level (beginner, intermediate, and advanced) and by target audience, with resources categorised accordingly.

Across both the FAIR and RDM training collections, a large number of resources provide beginner- and intermediate-level guidance aimed at students and researchers, whereas advanced-level training materials are considerably less prevalent. Such advanced resources are, however, particularly important for both researchers and data stewards

seeking to deepen their expertise in FAIR data management. In particular, there is a need for training on topics such as controlled vocabularies, metadata standards, file formats, interoperability processes, (trustworthy digital) repositories, and long-term data curation, which would significantly broaden the available training portfolio for FAIR and RDM. In addition, the number of resources explicitly targeting citizens as a target audience remains relatively limited.

To determine whether these gaps represent a critical shortcoming, it is first necessary to assess and map the needs of the pilot institutions involved in PATTERN. If demand is primarily concentrated at the beginner and intermediate levels, addressing advanced-level gaps may be of lower priority. Conversely, if there is substantial interest in advanced training, several pathways could be pursued. These include the reuse and adaptation of the FAIRsFAIR data steward training curriculum, as well as collaboration with ongoing initiatives such as skills4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT, which are actively developing training in these areas. Close liaison with such projects would also be valuable for aligning RDM and data steward training roadmaps for both researchers and support staff. Similar considerations apply to the further development of training materials specifically aimed at citizens.

Limitations and gaps

The mapping exercise benefited from contributions by a large and diverse group of PATTERN partners, complemented by resources collected through a survey disseminated within the consortium. This approach resulted in a substantial and high-quality collection of training materials. Nevertheless, it is likely that some relevant resources were not captured. The sharing of educational and training materials is not yet common practice, which means that high-quality resources may remain difficult to identify due to limited visibility, accessibility, or dissemination. While the current collection provides a strong basis for adoption, reuse, and further development within PATTERN, continued monitoring of emerging and previously undiscovered resources is necessary. Closer collaboration with related initiatives conducting similar mapping activities (e.g. Skills4EOSC) would help mitigate the risk of omissions.

Not all mapped resources are equally suitable for reuse in WP2. In particular, recordings of live or synchronous training events and webinars often present limitations due to their length, context-specific focus, and, in some cases, suboptimal technical quality. Such resources are therefore unlikely to be directly reusable and would require substantial editing or re-recording to be adapted for new training activities.

At the same time, several resources stand out as particularly promising for reuse or adaptation, including structured online courses with clearly defined learning objectives and pedagogical frameworks. Examples include *How to be FAIR with your data: A teaching and training handbook for higher education institutions*, the *FOSTER Open Science Training Handbook* (although in need of updating), and *Essentials 4 Data Support*. In addition, some non-training resources—such as *The Turing Way* or the *CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide*—could form valuable components of training

if appropriately embedded within lesson structures and supplemented with learning outcomes and exercises.

Finally, providing training resources alone is insufficient to ensure impact. A key challenge lies in supporting their adoption at institutional level. For this reason, PATTERN pilot activities should focus not only on testing training content, but also on evaluating processes of uptake and integration within existing curricula and organisational practices. A demand-driven gap analysis at pilot institutions—examining current provision, needs, and ambitions—will be essential. In this respect, the work in WP4 on policy development will play a critical role in enabling sustainable institutional uptake of PATTERN training materials.

Citizen Science

Summary

For Citizen Science (CS) training resources, PATTERN builds on the work of two previous EU-funded projects, EU-Citizen.Science and TIME4CS. Training resources identified through these earlier initiatives that were still accessible at the time of the mapping were incorporated into the PATTERN dataset (66 resources in total), and their metadata were extended to meet PATTERN requirements. In addition, PATTERN identified 43 new CS training resources.

Overall, a comparable number of course-type training activities (e-learning modules, courses, and workshops; n = 54) and non-course training materials (static resources and webinars/lectures; n = 55) were collected for Citizen Science (see Table X). The majority of course-type trainings are delivered online (43), while 11 are or were offered in person. Although no fully blended training formats were identified, several online trainings are designed in ways that make them adaptable to blended delivery.

Static resources constitute the largest share of non-course materials (n = 43) and include toolkits, guides, handbooks, and short videos, while the remaining 12 resources consist of recordings of webinars or lectures. Most course-type Citizen Science trainings are relatively recent, with the majority dating from 2021–2023. By contrast, some static resources, such as guides and handbooks, date back as early as 2012 but continue to be actively disseminated and used.

Table 6 Citizen Science resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (43), in-person (11)	Static resource (43), webinar / lecture (12)
Expertise level	Beginner (28), Intermediate (13), Advanced (4), All (9)	Beginner (10), Intermediate (4), Advanced (3), All (38)

Main audience	All audiences (15), All researchers / academics (14), Students (3), Doctoral / PhD students (3), General public (3), Research support (2), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (8), Other (4)	All audiences (17), All researchers / academics (24), General public (9), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (3), Other (1)
Learning outcomes	Stated/easily understood from description (51), not stated & not easily understood (3)	Stated/easily understood from description (52); not stated & not easily understood (3)
Access	Open access (47), restricted access (4), Paid access (3)	Open access (54), Paid access (1)
Scientific domain	Generic (38), Natural Sciences (13), Medical & Health Sciences (1), Social Sciences and Humanities (2)	Generic (23), Natural Sciences (31), Engineering & Technology (1)
Primary language	Croatian (1), English (40), German (8), Greek (1), Hungarian (1), Swedish (1)	Dutch (1), English (53)
Qualification	Badge (19), Certification (6), Accreditation (1), ECTS (6), Other (2), None (6)	None (55)

The majority of course-type Citizen Science resources are suitable for beginners (28), while intermediate-level learners are also well supported (13 resources). Most static resources are designed for all levels (38), followed by beginner level (10). Only a small number of resources explicitly target advanced learners, both for course-type trainings (4) and static materials (3).

Resources primarily address all audiences and all researchers/academics, reflecting an emphasis on broad dissemination of Citizen Science principles and practices among potential participants, project initiators, and coordinators. In addition, a subset of courses specifically targets trainers and educators (8), as well as “other” audiences (4), including Citizen Science project managers, librarians, and policy or decision makers.

Learning outcomes are generally well documented or can be clearly inferred from resource descriptions. In several cases, resources specify learning objectives rather than learning outcomes; however, given that these courses have typically been piloted and implemented, a close correspondence between objectives and outcomes was assumed and recorded interchangeably. Most resources are open access and free of charge. In some instances—particularly for MOOCs—paid upgrades are available, offering additional features such as increased interaction with tutors and peers or formal certification. Restricted-access courses (4) are mainly linked to formal

education contexts or targeted at early career researchers, for example Master’s-level courses or Summer Schools aimed at PhD and postdoctoral researchers.

With respect to scientific domain, generic training and training in the natural sciences are most prevalent. The latter reflects the prominence of environmental and biodiversity-related Citizen Science projects, where public participation substantially extends both project scale and societal impact. In contrast, considerably fewer training opportunities are specifically tailored to the humanities, social sciences, engineering and technology, or medical and health sciences.

The primary language of delivery is English, although several course-type trainings are offered in German (8) and single courses are available in Croatian, Greek, Hungarian, and Swedish. In addition, some English-language resources have been translated into multiple languages, which is not fully reflected in the quantitative tables because translations were not logged as separate entries. One example is the Open Science Training Handbook, which is available in Portuguese, Spanish, and Italian, and is scheduled to be released in Greek, German, and French.

Most course-type trainings award badges of completion (24), a format commonly used in online training, which constitutes the majority of offerings. Certificates of participation, classified under “Other” in the PATTERN framework, are also relatively common (10). A smaller number of courses provide certificates of completion (4) or formal accreditation (1). ECTS credits are available in six cases, typically where courses are embedded in formal education programmes, while nine course-type trainings do not offer any formal qualification.

Content themes of available training and identified gaps

To analyse the content of Citizen Science training resources, the TIME4CS content-theme framework was adopted. This framework includes the following themes: Introduction to Citizen Science; Engagement; Communication; Best practices; Citizen Science stories; Data quality and standards; Project management; Regulations and ethics; Research design and methods; Co-creation; Impact; Links with formal education; Empowerment; Evaluation of Citizen Science; Project sustainability; Reflections on science; and Funding.

In addition, the theme “Institutional change” was included to reflect emerging trends related to embedding Citizen Science within research performing organisations and institutions, which constitutes a central focus of the Time4CS project.

The number of training resources per content theme identified through the mapping is presented in the table below, providing an overview of areas that are well covered as well as those where gaps in training provision remain.

Table 7 Citizen Science content themes

Content theme	Number of training activities
Introduction to CS	62

Engagement	50
Communication	40
Best practices	39
CS stories	28
Data quality and standards	28
Project management	25
Regulations and ethics	23
Research design and methods	22
Co-creation	21
Impact	20
Link with formal education	17
Empowerment	15
Evaluation of citizen science	12
Project sustainability	8
Reflections on science	8
Funding	2
Institutional change	1

The intersection between Citizen Science and diversity and inclusion, particularly from an intersectional perspective, remains an evident gap in the mapped training resources. Only two static resources address this dimension, reporting on initiatives that engaged young people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and senior citizens as citizen scientists and resulting primarily in sets of recommendations. Furthermore, the integration of local and traditional knowledge, as well as training that addresses communication challenges and opportunities linked to traditional belief systems, is poorly represented in the resources collected.

Training activities aimed at supporting research-performing organisations in developing roadmaps for Citizen Science implementation, falling under the content theme Institutional change, represent an emerging area of provision and are being explicitly developed within the Time4CS project. However, additional gaps identified in Time4CS—most notably training related to the development of Citizen Science policies and guidelines and to fundraising—persist and remain insufficiently addressed in the current training landscape.

Limitations and gaps

The mapping of Citizen Science training resources revealed several limitations and gaps. Beyond challenges related to identifying materials in different languages, terminological diversity added complexity to the mapping exercise. Citizen Science is referred to by a range of alternative terms (e.g. public participation in scientific research, community science, civic science, participatory monitoring), with varying national preferences and linguistic adaptations. In addition, the term citizen science itself is not universally accepted as inclusive, particularly in the United States, where it may be perceived as excluding non-nationals.

The vast majority of mapped resources are available in English, reflecting both its role as the lingua franca of scientific collaboration and practical limits of the mapping process. While resources in national languages undoubtedly exist, they are often harder to identify unless providers actively promote their availability. In-person training activities and training offered by private providers were also underrepresented, largely due to time, access, and methodological constraints.

In terms of reuse potential, many webinars and recorded materials suffer from limited interactivity, variable technical quality, or context-specific delivery, reducing their suitability for direct reuse in WP2. Similarly, some US-based resources, while thematically relevant, are closely tied to national legal or institutional frameworks and would require substantial adaptation for a European context.

Conversely, resources from the EU-Citizen.Science platform, which have undergone moderation and quality screening, represent a particularly strong basis for WP2 reuse. More than twenty resources have already been identified for further assessment in Task 1.3, with interactive, problem-based formats generally perceived as the most attractive for reuse. At the same time, there is a clear need to better address the skills requirements of advanced learners, for example in building sustainable communities of engagement or embedding Citizen Science within organisations through policies, governance, and fundraising.

Finally, several thematic gaps remain. Training at the intersection of Citizen Science with diversity, inclusion, and societal concerns (e.g. special needs, generational diversity, gender diversity, local and traditional knowledge systems) is limited. Continued emphasis is also needed on institutional embedding of Citizen Science to ensure long-term sustainability. Given the strong focus on environmental projects, introducing “Environmental Citizen Science” as a distinct content theme—and, more broadly, refining thematic descriptors—could support more granular analysis and future training development.

Research Integrity

Summary

Any research performing organisation should offer research ethics and integrity (REI) training. These trainings aim to facilitate and promote high quality research, high standards of ethics and integrity and compliance, and create and foster a better and more responsible research environment. That complex area covers moral, ethical, legal, but also – cultural, gender, inclusion and equity issues. As a consequence, the REI trainings are very diverse, covering different topics, i.e., policies on data management, open access, supervision and mentoring, authorship, handling alleged cases of research misconduct, and many others. The overall framework depends on the

organisation size, capacity, resources, main goals, strategic developments, and the existing legal and administrative framework.

Mapped resources

Table 8 Research integrity resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (10), in-person (4), blended (1)	Static resource (14), webinar / lecture (3)
Expertise level	Beginner (7), Intermediate (4), Advanced (1), All (3)	Beginner (2), Intermediate (3), Advanced (1), All (10)
Main audience	All audiences (2), All researchers / academics (5), Students (3), Doctoral / PhD students (3), General public (0), Research support (0), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (0), Other (0)	All audiences (12), All researchers / academics (4), Students (0), Doctoral / PhD students (1), General public (0), Research support (0), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (0), Other (0)
Learning outcomes	Specified (2), non-specified (13)	Specified (15), non-specified (3)
Scientific domain	Generic (7), Natural Sciences (0), Engineering & Technology (0), Medical & Health Sciences (7), Social Sciences and Humanities (1)	Generic (16), Natural Sciences (1), Engineering & Technology (0), Medical & Health Sciences (0), Social Sciences and Humanities (0)
Primary language	English (14), Italian (1)	English (16)
Qualification	Badge (3), Certification (9), Accreditation (0), ECTS (1), Other (0), None (2)	Certification (3), None (16)

The data summary presented in Table 8 points to a rich and diverse set of training resources and non-course materials available in the field of Research Integrity. Training activities are predominantly delivered online, while non-course materials comprise a balanced mix of static resources and webinars. Most resources are designed primarily for beginner-level learners, but a substantial proportion also addresses the needs of intermediate and advanced audiences. Both training and non-course resources target a

broad range of audiences, from students to established academics, with the majority being cross-disciplinary in scope.

Table 9 Research integrity content themes

Content themes	Number of trainings
Research integrity	21
Research ethics	11
Responsible Research and good scientific practice	12
Ethical review	8
Biomedical Ethics	7
Informed consent	11
Privacy and confidentiality	4
Data practices and management	15
Intellectual property and authorship	0
Declaration of interests	4
Research misconduct and questionable Research practices	13
Governance	13
Vulnerable participants	3
Moral-compass: values-based trainings	2
Research collaborations	0
Research environment	6
Publication and communication	4
Open Science	6
Supervision and mentoring	13

As seen in Teable 9, a wide range of training areas is represented under the overarching concept of Research Integrity. Prominently covered topics include Responsible research and good scientific practice, Data practices and management, and Supervision and mentoring, each of which encompasses a substantial number of content themes, indicating both the breadth and depth of existing training provision. In addition, areas such as Research misconduct and questionable research practices, Informed consent, and Governance are robustly represented, each with more than ten associated content themes.

The Governance theme—linked to topics such as implementation, assessment and evaluation, management, as well as related themes including research environment and research collaboration—emerges as a key area in recent developments in Research Integrity training. In particular, the Research environment theme, as conceptualised in the SOPs4RI project taxonomy, addresses issues that were previously underrepresented in Research Integrity training, such as hyper-competition, harmful publication pressure, detrimental power imbalances, and conflicts. At the same time, it highlights positive institutional practices, including fair, transparent, and responsible policies for

researcher assessment, recruitment, and promotion, as well as the promotion of diversity and inclusion.

Core values such as collegiality, openness, reflexivity, and shared responsibility as essential elements of a healthy research environment are explicitly addressed through innovative approaches such as the “Moral-compass: virtues-based training” methodology. These approaches, which emphasise research culture and researchers’ well-being, are being actively promoted by several training providers and EU-funded projects.

Finally, Research ethics, Biomedical ethics, and Ethical review are addressed across a considerable number of training resources. This reflects an important and emerging shift within the fields of research ethics and Research Integrity toward a more integrated and holistic approach, where ethical and integrity-related topics are increasingly addressed together rather than through narrowly separated or discipline-specific courses.

Limitations and gaps

The mapping highlights several significant gaps in Research Integrity training provision. Intellectual Property and Authorship and Research Collaborations are not represented in the content themes, indicating a substantial lack of training in these critical areas. This is a notable deficiency given their central role in maintaining responsible and ethical research practices. In addition, training coverage is limited for topics such as Privacy and Confidentiality, Vulnerable Participants, and the interface between Open Science and Research Integrity, suggesting that existing provision in these areas is less comprehensive than in other domains.

Further gaps may exist beyond those captured by the current content themes. Emerging and underrepresented topics—such as AI and other new technologies, cultural competence in research, and power dynamics within research collaborations—are likely to require greater attention in future training. Moreover, there is a clear need for a more discipline-sensitive approach, particularly for non-biomedical fields, as well as for training that addresses the specific needs of groups such as citizen scientists.

The mapping process itself faced several limitations. Most notably, restricted access to some training programmes limited the ability to assess content depth and quality, which may have led to the underrepresentation of certain training areas. This lack of access also made it difficult to determine the suitability of some resources for reuse in WP2, particularly where learning outcomes, formats, or pedagogical approaches could not be fully evaluated.

Nevertheless, a small number of resources stand out as promising candidates for further analysis in Task 1.3. These include the Dilemma Game, which offers an engaging and adaptable approach to learning about Research Integrity, and virtues-based “Moral-compass” trainings, which support reflection on research culture, collegiality, and shared responsibility. Such approaches are particularly well suited to inter- and

transdisciplinary groups, leadership training, and mixed-career audiences. In addition, greater emphasis on training related to implementation, governance, and evaluation within the research environment would support the longer-term development of a responsible research culture.

Finally, future progress would benefit from stronger synergies with existing and emerging training initiatives and platforms, including projects such as ORION, PRO-RES, GoEQIPD, FAITH, iRECs, ROSiE, and ENERI. Strategic collaboration with these initiatives can help ensure that Research Integrity training remains up to date, avoids duplication of effort, and addresses both current gaps and emerging needs.

Gender, Non-discrimination, and Inclusion in Research

Summary

The Horizon Europe framework programme builds on and extends Horizon 2020 by advancing a more inclusive concept of gender equality and diversity within research and innovation (R&I) institutions. Central to this approach is the adoption of an intersectional perspective, which recognises the interplay between gender and other social categories and identities—such as ethnicity and race (including migrants and refugees), social class and socioeconomic status, gender identity and sexual orientation (LGBTI+), and disability. By addressing these interlocking systems of power, Horizon Europe seeks to more effectively capture the multiple and interacting forms of inequality experienced by actors across the R&I system.

Related measures include, first, expanded support for gender research aimed at deepening understanding of gender equality and its intersections with other forms of inequality; and second, incentives that encourage the adoption of Gender Equality Plans, alongside broader strategies addressing diversity, non-discrimination, and inclusion through comprehensive approaches to institutional change.

To equip researchers with the skills required to recognise and apply Open RRI values, knowledge and competencies related to gender equality, non-discrimination, and inclusion should be embedded across researcher education, research projects, and the wider research environment. Integrating these dimensions into training and practice is essential for fostering inclusive, responsible, and socially responsive research cultures.

Mapped resources

Table 10 Gender, non-discrimination, and inclusion in research resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	20	44
Expertise level	Beginner (5), Intermediate (1), All (14)	Beginner (8), Advanced (1), All (32)
Main audience	All audiences (7), All researchers / academics	All audiences (18), All researchers / academics

	(6), Students (1), Doctoral / PhD students (3), Postdoctoral researchers (2), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (1)	(23), Doctoral / PhD students (1), Postdoctoral researchers (1), Research support (1)
Learning outcomes	Specified (20)	Specified (44)
Scientific domain	Generic (17), Engineering & Technology (1), Medical & Health Sciences (1), Social Sciences and Humanities (1)	Generic (35), Engineering & Technology (2), Medical & Health Sciences (1), Social Sciences and Humanities (5)
Primary language	English (19), French (1)	English (42), Dutch (1), Italian (1)
Qualification	Certification (1), ECTS (1), None for others	ECTS (1), None for others

As shown in Table 10, the majority of resources collected consist of static materials and webinars, which often provide solid overviews of diversity, non-discrimination, and inclusion in Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) training. Although these resources are not always regularly updated, many remain valuable—particularly guidelines supporting the development of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) for organisations seeking EU funding. A smaller number of resources take the form of interactive trainings, which show greater potential for replication and sustained participant engagement.

In terms of expertise level, most resources target all levels (14 training courses and 32 non-course materials), followed by beginner-level provision (5 and 8 respectively). Resources aimed at intermediate and advanced learners are rare (one training and one non-course resource, respectively).

A similar pattern is evident with regard to target audiences. Most resources address all audiences or all researchers/academics, reflecting an emphasis on broad accessibility and awareness-raising. More targeted provision for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, students, research support staff, and trainers is comparatively limited.

With respect to learning outcomes, the majority of resources specify learning outcomes explicitly or allow them to be readily inferred from the content (20 trainings and 44 non-course materials), supporting informed selection and reuse.

Most resources are generic in disciplinary scope, with only a handful addressing specific scientific domains. Domain-specific coverage is limited to isolated cases in engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, and the social sciences, while natural sciences, humanities, and agricultural sciences are not explicitly targeted.

English is the dominant language of delivery for both training and non-course materials. The prevalence of English likely reflects both the working language of international project consortia and the practical limits of the mapping exercise, rather than an

absence of resources in other languages. English-language resources are, however, more readily adaptable for reuse by PATTERN partners.

Finally, formal qualifications are rarely offered: most resources do not indicate any form of certification or credit. Only a small number of exemptions were identified, including isolated cases of certification and ECTS credit.

Content themes

Table 11 Gender, non-discrimination, and inclusion in research content themes

Content theme	Number of resources
Gender Equality	53
Diversity	35
Intersectionality	19
Inclusion	22
Gender Equality Plan	30
Gender Budgeting	10
Gender-Based Violence	5
Gender Dimension in Research	31
Gender Sensitive Research	24
Organizational Culture	4
Gender+	3
Intercultural Communication	3

The most frequently addressed theme across the mapped resources is Gender Equality (53), framed as a broad foundational concept encompassing a fundamental human right, equal access to resources and opportunities, and the equal valuing of different behaviours, aspirations, and needs regardless of gender. This framing is highly relevant to the academic and scientific context.

Several more specific gender-related themes are also well represented, including Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) (30), Gender Dimension in Research (31), Gender-Sensitive Research (24), Gender Budgeting (10), Combatting Gender-Based Violence (5), and Gender+ approaches (3). These topics are addressed either through dedicated, in-depth training activities or embedded within broader curricula covering multifaceted gender equality issues.

Overall, the content of gender-related training resources can be grouped into three main areas:

- Integrating a gender perspective into research content, project design, agreements, and research outputs.
- Supportive and enabling measures, including counselling, awareness-raising, legal support (e.g. in cases of gender-based violence), funding mechanisms, and dissemination activities that strengthen gender-sensitive research practices.
- Gender equality within research teams and organisational environments, with a focus on women’s leadership, equitable distribution of power and

decision-making positions, and fair access to resources and scientific recognition.

At the same time, the overall trend in training provision is to move beyond an exclusive focus on gender. Concepts such as Intersectionality (19), Diversity (35), Inclusion (22), Organisational Culture (4), and Intercultural Communication (3) increasingly appear as distinct yet interconnected themes. This shift is also reflected in the evolution of Gender Equality Plans, which are now promoted by the European Union as inclusive Gender Equality Plans, emphasising that non-discrimination extends beyond gender alone. Such approaches explicitly address factors including social status, age, religion, disability, cultural background, and other dimensions of inequality, with the overarching aim of fostering lasting changes in mindsets, organisational cultures, attitudes, and behaviours.

Limitations and gaps

Several limitations and gaps can be identified in the current landscape of training resources on Gender Equality, Inclusion, and Non-Discrimination. First, the predominance of static resources and webinars limits reusability and scalability. While such materials often provide solid introductory content, their limited interactivity, infrequent updating, and—in the case of webinars—considerable length reduce their potential for adaptation and replication in new training contexts.

Second, training provision is strongly concentrated on Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), reflecting the European Commission's requirement for organisations seeking EU funding to adopt and implement a GEP at institutional level. While this focus has increased demand for training on GEP design and implementation, other inclusion-related topics remain insufficiently covered, particularly gender-based violence, despite its continued prevalence within academic and research environments.

Third, most available materials are designed for all audiences and all expertise levels and are largely introductory in nature. Although such training is essential for awareness-raising, there is a clear need for more specialised and advanced provision, including training targeted specifically at trainers, educators, and institutional leaders to support cascade models of knowledge transfer. Examples of underrepresented advanced topics include monitoring and evaluation of GEP implementation and assessing their tangible institutional impacts, such as reductions in gender-based violence or increases in women's representation at senior levels.

A further gap relates to qualifications and incentives. Most resources do not offer certification, ECTS, or other forms of formal recognition. Embedding training within qualification frameworks could increase uptake, strengthen learner commitment, and promote deeper engagement through assessment and feedback mechanisms.

The mapping exercise itself was subject to several limitations. Time constraints and the breadth of relevant themes meant that not all emerging or forthcoming resources could be captured. In addition, language barriers likely resulted in the underrepresentation of

high-quality materials produced in languages not spoken by the mappers. The dominance of online formats also suggests that in-person trainings—which are harder to identify and assess without direct participation or documented feedback—may be underrepresented.

Despite these constraints, the mapped resources are considered representative of the current state of the art in Gender Equality, Inclusion, and Non-Discrimination training, capturing key trends in content, pedagogical approaches, and delivery formats. While static webinar recordings are generally less suitable for direct reuse in WP2, more recent materials may still be useful for identifying potential speakers and expertise. In contrast, several resources stand out as particularly promising for reuse or adaptation, including those from GE Academy, GENDERACTION (GEAR tool), ACT (GEAM tool), RRI Tools, Trinity College Dublin, and LPI, which combine relevance, clarity, interactivity, and up-to-date content.

Finally, many of the more widely used and attractive resources rely on problem-based and case-based learning, emphasising reflection and dialogue. While GEP-related training and alignment with EU funding requirements dominate current provision, other aspects of intersectionality and inclusion—such as the integration of migrants and other vulnerable groups into responsible research and higher education—remain underrepresented and warrant greater attention in future PATTERN training development.

Dissemination and Exploitation of Results

Summary

In the contemporary research and innovation landscape, high-quality training in dissemination and exploitation of research results is essential. These activities are key horizontal components of publicly funded research and are increasingly expected to be embedded throughout the lifecycle of EU-funded projects.

As research outputs proliferate and circulate at unprecedented speed, generating new knowledge alone is no longer sufficient. Researchers are also required to communicate effectively with diverse audiences—including scientific peers, policymakers, industry, and society at large—and to ensure that research findings are taken up, reused, and translated into societal, economic, or policy impact. Strategic approaches to dissemination and exploitation support collaboration, strengthen innovation ecosystems, enhance the visibility and relevance of research, and contribute to long-term sustainability of research investments.

Training in dissemination and exploitation equips researchers with the skills needed to bridge the gap between knowledge production and real-world application. By strengthening these competencies, research systems can better connect academic excellence with societal needs, foster innovation, and maximise the value and impact of publicly funded research.

Resources mapped

Table 12 Dissemination and exploitation of research results resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (9), in-person (9), blended (4)	Static resource (6), webinar / lecture (7)
Expertise level	Beginner (17), Intermediate (1), Advanced (1), All (3)	Beginner (7), All (6)
Main audience	All audiences (4), All researchers / academics (7), Students (4), Doctoral / PhD students (7)	All researchers / academics (9), Doctoral / PhD students (1), research support (3)
Learning outcomes	Stated/easily understood from description (17), not stated & not easily understood (5)	Stated/easily understood from description (11); not stated & not easily understood (2)
Access	Open access (2), restricted access (5), Paid access (13), not specified (2)	Open access (9), restricted access (1), Paid access (3)
Scientific domain	Generic (15), Natural Sciences (4), Engineering & Technology (1), Medical & Health Sciences (2)	Generic (12), Social Sciences (1)
Primary language	English (14), German (2), Italian (6)	English (7), Italian (6)
Qualification	Certification (10), ECTS (5), Other (1), None (6)	None (13)

This PATTERN training area brings together two closely related themes—Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results—which are essential horizontal components of contemporary research and innovation activities. The mapping was conducted primarily by SISSA, UniSR, and APRE, with additional contributions from AU, MLE1, and responses collected through the consortium survey. A subset of the identified resources (11) overlaps with the Science Communication training area, reflecting the strong conceptual and practical links between these domains.

In total, 21 course-type training resources (e-learning modules, courses, and workshops) and 14 non-course materials (static resources and webinars/lectures) were collected (see Table X). Course-type trainings are delivered through a mix of online (9), in-person (9), and blended (4) formats, while non-course materials consist of static resources (6) and webinars or recorded lectures (7).

The majority of course-type resources are aimed at beginner-level learners (17). Similarly, static resources are primarily designed for beginners (7) or for all expertise levels (6), indicating a clear emphasis on introductory provision. By contrast, there is a notable shortage of resources targeting intermediate and advanced learners. With respect to target audiences, resources cater mainly to researchers/academics and doctoral/PhD students, with learning outcomes generally stated or easily identifiable. A limited number of static resources specifically address research support staff (3).

Access conditions differ between resource types. Most static resources are open access (9), whereas the majority of course-type trainings require paid access (13). Both types of resources are largely generic in disciplinary scope, although a small number of courses explicitly target the Natural Sciences (4), Engineering and Technology (1), and Medical and Health Sciences (2). The primary language of delivery is English, followed by Italian, reflecting the language profiles of the PATTERN partners involved in this mapping exercise.

Several course-type trainings award a certificate of completion (10), and a smaller subset offers ECTS credits (5), indicating integration within formal education contexts. However, six course-type trainings do not provide any formal qualification.

Content themes

Table 13 Dissemination and exploitation of research results content themes

Content themes	Number of training activities
Scientific and Technical Writing	12
Multimedia	8
Intellectual property; Copyright	8
Tools for Presentation	7
Business plans	7
Public Speaking	5
Strategy	5
Social Media & Digital Communication	4
Business/Go-to-market	4
Social and economic impact	4
Technology transfer	3
Investments and funding	3
Entrepreneurship	3
Regulatory Affairs	2
Industry collaborations	1
Market analysis	1
Proof-of-Concept experiments	1
Team creation	1

The content themes used to analyse the dissemination and exploitation training resources were derived directly from the themes explicitly addressed in the collected materials. The distribution of resources across content themes is presented in Table 13. Overall, dissemination-related themes are the most prominent, particularly scientific

and technical writing (12 resources), multimedia communication (8), and presentation tools and techniques (7). At the same time, several content themes linked to the exploitation of research results are also well represented, notably intellectual property (7) and business planning (7), indicating a balanced—though dissemination-leaning—coverage of the two domains.

Limitations and gaps

Several limitations and gaps were identified in the dissemination and exploitation training landscape. Most notably, exploitation-related themes are underrepresented compared to dissemination. While dissemination topics such as writing and presentation are well covered, social and economic impact—treated as a combined theme—shows a clear imbalance, with only one resource explicitly focusing on social impact, indicating a significant gap.

The mapping itself was constrained by limited partner involvement and allocated effort for this theme, which likely resulted in incomplete coverage. Additional relevant resources may exist but were not captured. At European level, training provision in dissemination and exploitation often mirrors funding application requirements, which can narrow scope and reduce diversity in available training content.

In terms of reuse, many webinars and recorded materials are poorly suited for WP2 due to limited learner engagement in asynchronous formats, variable technical quality, difficulty locating relevant content within long recordings, and uncertainty about timeliness after the live event. Moreover, access barriers are significant: many course-type materials are paid or restricted, while open-access resources are frequently static, context-specific, and aimed at broad audiences, limiting their applicability to RRI-focused training. As a result, there is a shortage of readily reusable materials for WP2.

To address these gaps, it is recommended that PATTERN systematically explore existing collections and catalogues to identify additional high-quality resources and broaden the pool of materials suitable for reuse and adaptation.

Science Communication (for media and policymakers)

Summary

Within the Open RRI framework, Science Communication plays a pivotal role in connecting researchers and society. Faced with contemporary challenges and the relationship between Science, Technology and Society, Science Communication proposes new forms of discourse on how scientific knowledge is produced, focusing not only on findings but on methodologies, implications and uncertainty.

Recently, Lewenstein and Baram-Tsabari (2022) conducted a comprehensive study of the design of science communication courses. The article proposes to organise courses in relation to the competences of those who participate in them, recognising different learning objectives just as different audiences are addressed.

This is the result of mapping the state of the art of science communication training activities in Europe, adding on the work previously done by two other projects (QUEST and GlobalSCAPE). The data collected cover key information about the courses (such as target group, level of experience, language of instruction etc.) and their content.

Mapped resources

Table 14 Science communication resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (22), in-person (66), blended (11)	Static resource (4), webinar / lecture (11)
Expertise level	Beginner (92), Intermediate (6), Advanced (1)	Beginner (10), Intermediate (3)
Main audience	All audiences (15), All researchers / academics (14), Students (66), Doctoral / PhD students (5), Postdoctoral researchers (1), Others (1)	All audiences (2), All researchers / academics (8), Doctoral / PhD students (3), Others (1)
Learning outcomes	Stated/easily understood from description (43)	Stated/easily understood from description (3)
Access	Open access (9), Restricted access (11), Paid access (75)	Open access (8), restricted access (4), Paid access (1)
Scientific domain	Generic (79), Natural Sciences (4), Engineering & Technology (4), Medical & Health Sciences (11); Humanities (1)	Generic (15)
Primary language	English (63), German (7), Italian (9), Croatian (1), Finnish (3), French (7), Norwegian (1), Portuguese (3), Spanish (5)	English (9), Italian (2), Croatian (1), Finnish (1), German (2)
Qualification	Certification (64), ECTS (12), Badge (2), Other (1), None (14)	Certification (2), ECTS (1), None (6)

A total of 114 Science Communication training activities (focusing on communication towards media and policymakers) currently active in Europe were identified, see Table 14. Of these, 99 are course-based training activities (including courses, workshops, and e-learning modules) and 15 are non-course materials (such as webinars, lectures, and static resources).

The majority of courses are designed primarily for students at beginner level, and most training activities require paid access. The considerable diversity observed in terms of target audiences and levels of experience can largely be explained by the fact that many of the identified Science Communication training activities are master’s-level programmes, typically lasting one or two years. These programmes are intended for individuals with little or no prior experience and provide comprehensive preparation for a professional career in science communication.

Science Communication is a recognised academic discipline with its own theoretical foundations and professional pathways. Consequently, master’s programmes differ substantially from shorter training activities, which are more commonly aimed at researchers seeking to develop specific communication skills rather than full professional qualifications.

With regard to scientific domain, most programmes adopt a generic approach, addressing science from multiple perspectives before offering specialised modules focused on particular topics or disciplines. A smaller number of training activities are explicitly tailored to communication within specific scientific fields, reflecting more targeted training needs.

Content themes

Table 15 Science communication content themes

Content themes	Number of training resources
Science Journalism	39
Multimedia	38
Social Media & Digital Communication	37
SC Theory	29
Science Museums & Science Centres	22
Health communication	19
Media Training	16
Institutional Communication & Public Relations	15
Environmental communication	13
Science Policy	11
Risk Communication	11
Communication with Policy Makers	7
Publishing	5
Event Organization	5
Communicating AI	3

The identified training topics place strong emphasis on the digital dimension of science communication. Most training activities include modules on multimedia production—such as video and audio editing or podcasting—as well as on social media and digital communication. Many courses also remain closely linked to science journalism and incorporate a theoretical component addressing foundational concepts in science

communication. While some programmes place greater weight on theory and others on practice, the majority combine both theoretical and practical elements.

A particularly strong thematic focus can be observed in health communication and communication related to environmental and climate change issues. Training activities connected to science museums and science centres are also present, although their geographical distribution remains uneven.

At the institutional level, training provision includes courses on institutional communication, media relations, and media training. The latter is specifically aimed at equipping researchers with the skills needed to interact effectively with the media, serving a different purpose from science journalism by focusing on representation and mediation rather than reporting.

In addition, several science communication courses address aspects related to Dissemination and Exploitation of research results, including skills such as preparing effective presentations, public speaking, and technical writing, highlighting the overlap between science communication and broader research impact activities.

Limitations and gaps

The mapping highlights several content-related gaps in current Science Communication training provision. Most courses are aimed at beginner-level learners and cover a broad range of topics at an introductory level. While this supports awareness-raising across diverse audiences, there is a notable lack of intermediate and advanced training, particularly for researchers seeking to deepen specific competencies. Closely related to this, training on engagement with policymakers is rare, reflecting the uneven institutionalisation of science–policy interfaces across countries. Strengthening provision in this area remains an important need.

Several emerging and underrepresented themes also warrant greater attention. These include communicating Artificial Intelligence, which is expected to become increasingly central to public discourse; diversity and inclusion as transversal issues aligned with PATTERN’s objectives; and, more generally, training on communicating scientific uncertainty and limitations, which is essential for fostering public trust. In addition, despite the growing importance of visual communication in digital and social media environments, there is a clear lack of dedicated training on graphics and visualisation, even at an introductory level.

The mapping process itself faced inherent limitations. Science Communication training activities vary widely in format, duration, and target audience, ranging from multi-year bachelor’s and master’s programmes to short, ad hoc workshops. While long-term degree programmes are relatively visible, short, locally organised training activities—often aimed specifically at researchers—are more difficult to identify, as they may be poorly advertised or leave no lasting online trace. As a result, such activities are likely underrepresented. The rapidly evolving nature of the field further implies that the mapping captures only a snapshot in time, necessitating periodic updates.

Language coverage also constitutes a limitation. While the mapping includes courses delivered in English and some major Western European languages, provision in Eastern and South-Eastern European languages is largely absent, reflecting both linguistic barriers and limited familiarity with local academic landscapes. This likely results in the omission of relevant regional training activities.

In terms of reuse for WP2, limited access to detailed course materials makes it difficult to assess the pedagogical quality and adaptability of many training activities. This challenge is compounded by the fact that the precise format of future WP2 training activities has not yet been fully defined. Nevertheless, several well-established programmes—particularly master’s courses and widely recognised online offerings—stand out as strong candidates for further analysis in Task 1.3 due to their clarity, structure, and international reputation.

Finally, the mapping underscores the importance of maintaining a balance between theoretical foundations and practical skill development in Science Communication training. While universally applicable modules are difficult to design given cultural and linguistic differences across countries, innovative approaches—especially those experimenting with digital and technological formats—offer promising models that merit further exploration within PATTERN.

Management and Leadership

Summary

In today’s rapidly evolving academic landscape—characterised by innovation, collaboration, and increasing interdisciplinarity—the role of researchers extends well beyond traditional scientific inquiry. In addition to domain-specific expertise, researchers are now expected to possess leadership and management competencies that enable them to steer complex projects, foster cross-disciplinary collaboration, and guide teams toward shared goals. This growing complexity has contributed to a redefinition of what it means to be a leader or manager within academic organisations.

Researchers are increasingly required to listen, connect, and motivate others, particularly early-career colleagues, while simultaneously developing their own leadership capacity and self-confidence. As they are often directly involved in managing colleagues at different career stages, they need skills in interpersonal communication, conflict resolution, emotional intelligence, and team dynamics. At the same time, the expanding boundaries of research require researchers to engage more actively with challenges traditionally associated with the business environment, including navigating funding landscapes, building strategic partnerships, and communicating research outcomes effectively to diverse stakeholders.

Expanding leadership and management training opportunities for researchers and the wider academic community therefore has the potential to generate transformative impacts, not only on individual careers but also on research organisations as a whole, strengthening their capacity to operate as hubs of innovation and excellence.

Mapped resources

Table 16 Management and leadership training resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Workshop (2), course (26), e-learning (8)	Static resource (3), webinar / lecture (8)
Expertise level	Beginner (12), Intermediate (8), Advanced (8), All (8)	Beginner (1), Intermediate (2), All (8)
Main audience	All audiences (2), All researchers / academics (9), Doctoral / PhD students (7), Postdoctoral researchers (7), Trainers / teachers / lectures (1), Research support (8), Others (1)	All audiences (7), All researchers / academics (3), General public (1)
Learning outcomes	Stated/easily understood from description (30)	Stated/easily understood from description (4)
Access	Open access (9), Restricted access (11), Paid access (75)	Open access (8), restricted access (4), Paid access (1)
Scientific domain	Generic (31), Natural Sciences (1), Engineering & Technology (1), Medical & Health Sciences (2); Social Science & Humanities (2)	Generic (11)
Primary language	English (30), German (2), Italian (2), French (2)	English (11)
Qualification	Certification (11), ECTS (1), Badge (1), Other (1), None (1)	None (4)

The mapping of existing learning opportunities for researchers in Management and Leadership skills collected a total of 47 resources provided by 33 different institutions. These resources are classified into proper training activities such as courses, workshops, and e-learning modules (36 resources), as well as non-course training materials such as webinars and static resources (11 resources).

Out of the 36 training activities identified, 15 were delivered online, 8 in a blended modality, and 10 were provided in person. 12 resources were available for beginners, 8 for intermediate learners, 8 for advanced learners, and 8 suitable for all expertise levels. The main audience for the training activities collected varied greatly: while 2 of them

targeted all audiences, others focused on specific groups such as researchers/academics (9), doctoral/PhD students (7), postdoctoral researchers (7), and research support staff (8), Trainers / teachers / lecturers (1) and other audiences (2). In terms of access rights, 18 courses required a fee to access the content, and 12 training activities had restricted access, being available exclusively to students affiliated with the organizing institution. Only 5 of them were published in open access. Regarding the scientific domain covered, the majority of resources (31 courses) were categorized as generic. The remaining courses had a more specific domain, with 1 training in engineering and technology, 2 in medical and health sciences, 1 in Natural Science and 1 in social sciences. English was the dominant language for accessing these materials, with 30 resources. Additionally, there were training activities conducted in French, German, and Italian, with each language accounting for 2 courses. Regarding the qualifications provided upon completion of the courses, only 11 courses provided certifications, 1 ECTS and 1 offered a badge.

In addition to the training activities, the mapping also collected a total of 11 non-course training materials, with 3 being static resources and 8 being webinars. These include, in terms of the expertise level required, 1 beginner-level resource, 2 intermediate-level resources, and 8 resources available for all expertise levels. The majority of non-course training materials were designed for a broad audience (7 resources for all audiences and 1 for the general public), while only 3 of them were specific to researchers and academics. All non-course training materials are classified as generic and are provided exclusively in English. None of them provided certification.

Content themes

Table 17 Management and leadership content themes

Content themes	Number of training activities
Team development	11
Conflict resolution	2
Coaching, Supporting and Leading Change	7
Managing Performance	7
Leadership	16
Communication styles and strategies	4
Problem solving	5
Recruitment	8
Empowerment	9
Project management	14
Resources management	3
Project sustainability	1
Cope with pressure	8
Self-organisation	11
Strategic thinking	8
Promote inclusion and diversity	5
Build mentor-mentee relationships	3

Networking	0
Career development	5

Almost all identified topics are covered by at least one resource, with many resources spanning multiple, overlapping themes. A substantial group of courses focuses on the skills required to be an effective research leader (16). Within this group, considerable attention is given to inclusive leadership, including strategies to address challenges such as gender and racial discrimination and the underrepresentation of minority ethnic groups among staff and students (Promoting inclusion and diversity: 5 resources; Empowerment: 9 resources).

There is also strong emphasis on researchers' well-being and work-related stress. Training offerings include resources on coping with pressure (8), self-organisation (10), and performance management (7). Project management is another well-represented area (14 resources), with most courses focusing on the administrative and financial management of research projects. However, resource management in a broader sense appears underdeveloped, being addressed by only three courses.

From a broader perspective, two important thematic gaps emerge. First, there is a need for expanded training on mentor–mentee relationships, which are essential for researcher development across career stages. Second, additional resources that support networking and connection-building—enabling researchers to engage more effectively with peers, mentors, and industry professionals—would help address a currently evident gap in networking-related training provision.

Limitations and gaps

The mapping of Management and Leadership training resources revealed several methodological and content-related limitations. A primary challenge was the restricted accessibility of many courses: the majority of identified training activities (37 out of 46) require either paid access or affiliation with the providing institution, typically a university. As a result, external users often have access only to limited descriptive information, making it difficult to assess course content, pedagogical approaches, learning outcomes, or overall quality. Even among open-access resources, limited reproducibility was observed, as many do not provide recordings, toolkits, or downloadable materials that could support reuse. The general lack of participant feedback and formal evaluation further constrained systematic quality assessment.

With regard to reuse in WP2, some courses were deemed unsuitable for further consideration. In particular, programmes such as Leadership Fundamentals (POLIMI Graduate School of Management), Team Leadership (SDA Bocconi), and Management Essentials were excluded due to their very broad target audience, strong orientation toward senior managers or executives, limited relevance to RRI, and high cost and long duration, all of which reduce their adaptability and scalability within the PATTERN context.

At the same time, a limited number of resources stand out as promising candidates for deeper quality analysis in Task 1.3. These include Leadership, Management, and Funding (University of Liverpool), which offers openly accessible and well-structured materials covering leadership, management, and funding within and beyond academia, and the Researcher Management and Leadership Training course on Coursera (University of Colorado), which provides comprehensive, modular, and interactive content relevant to principal investigators (although certification requires payment). Additional value is found in webinars and static collections such as Leadership and Management as a Scientist (NIGMS), Online Sessions on Well-being & Academia (Circle U.), and Leadership Development for Principal Investigators (Vitae), which are adaptable due to their flexible formats.

Institution-specific programmes, such as The Edinburgh Leader, The Aspiring Manager, and Equality and Diversity Essentials (University of Edinburgh), also offer high-quality, well-structured materials, though access restrictions limit direct reuse. Finally, resources such as the Research Management and Leadership Curriculum (IREX) and Leaders in Research Management (EARMA), while sometimes lacking detailed descriptions, provide clear structural outlines that can inform and inspire the development of future PATTERN training materials.

Open Science & General RRI

Summary and mapped resources

During the mapping exercise and data collection, several resources were identified that cut across the eight pillars of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). These materials are best characterised as Open Science or general RRI resources. Where relevant, the mapping workbook was expanded to capture these materials (see Tables 18 and 19). They are included here for completeness but do not constitute a core focus of the PATTERN project.

In total, 51 training resources were collected under the Open Science category, comprising 24 course-type training activities (e-learning modules, courses, and workshops) and 27 non-course materials (static resources and webinars/lectures). Course-type trainings were predominantly online (20) and primarily aimed at beginners (11) or all expertise levels (7), with a smaller number suitable for advanced learners (3). Similarly, static resources were largely designed for all expertise levels (14) or beginners (9), with four addressing intermediate-level learners.

The main target audiences for Open Science resources were researchers and academics (9 course-type trainings and 21 static resources), followed by all audiences (5 and 3 respectively). Some course-type trainings also targeted doctoral/PhD students (4) and other audiences (5), including private-sector actors, civil servants, and software developers. The majority of Open Science resources were open access, discipline-independent, and delivered in English, with a small number available in other languages such as French, German, Italian, Portuguese, and Greek.

Under the General RRI category, 15 training resources were identified, including 9 course-type trainings and 6 non-course materials. All General RRI resources were available in English and were mostly domain independent, although a small number addressed specific fields, including Natural Sciences and Engineering & Technology (one e-learning module) and Medical and Health Sciences (two static resources).

Table 18 Open science resources

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (20), in-person (2), blended (2)	Static resource (21), webinar / lecture (6)
Expertise level	Beginner (11), Intermediate (3), Advanced (3) All (7)	Beginner (9), Intermediate (4), All (14)
Main audience	All audiences (5), All researchers / academics (9), Students (1), Doctoral / PhD students (4), Others (5)	All audiences (3), All researchers / academics (21), Students (1), Doctoral / PhD students (2)
Access	Open access (19), Restricted access (2), Not specified (2)	Open access (25), Not specified (2)
Scientific domain	Generic (23), Social Science & Humanities (1)	Generic (24), Social Science & Humanities (3)
Primary language	English (20), German (1), Greek (1), French (2)	English (21), French (1), Italian (4), Portuguese (1)

Table 19 General RRI resources (metadat not available for expertise level, audience and access)

	Training materials (e-learning, courses, workshops)	Non-course training materials (static resources, webinars)
Training mode	Online (8), in-person (1)	Static resource (6)
Scientific domain	Generic (8), Natural Science & Engineering (1)	Generic (4), Medical & Health Sciences (2)
Primary language	English (9)	English (6)

Content themes

The distribution of resources and training activities across content themes is presented in the tables below, for general Open Science (Table 20) and general RRI (Table 21), respectively. Content themes with a higher number of associated resources reflect areas of broader interest and more extensive training provision, whereas less frequently represented themes may indicate more specialised or niche training topics.

Table 20 Open science content themes

Content themes	Number of training activities
Open Data	41
Open Access	31
Open Science tools	23
Open reproducible research	20
Open Science definition	19
Open Software/Open Source	18
Open Science evaluation	17
Open methodology	14
Open Science guidelines	14
Open Science policies	14
Open Notebooks	11
Citizen Science	10
IPR and legal skills	10
Open Peer Review	9
Open educational resources	9
Open Science projects	8
train the trainer	4
Research Integrity and OS	2

Table 21 General RRI content themes

Content themes	Number of training activities
Implementing RRI	10
Research Integrity	10
Science Communication	8
Open Access	7
Citizen Science	7
Open Science	7
Gender	7
Governance	5
FAIR data & RDM	5
Dissemination	4
organisational support for OS	4
Diversity & Inclusion	3
Reproducibility in research	2
Exploitation and IPR	0

Limitations and gaps

The mapping of general Open Science and general RRI training resources was not a primary objective of the PATTERN project. As a result, the materials collected in these categories do not constitute a comprehensive overview, but rather an indicative selection captured when resources were relevant across multiple RRI pillars.

Most of the identified resources have not yet undergone detailed quality assessment. In general, materials that are strongly embedded in national contexts tend to be less suitable for reuse within PATTERN, as their content may not translate well across countries. For example, while the video Open Science: what, how & why? is well produced and widely viewed, its framing is largely tailored to the Dutch context and would require adaptation to be relevant at European level. In addition, aspects such as representation and gender balance are not always adequately addressed.

It is not yet clear to what extent WP2 will require dedicated training materials on general Open Science or general RRI. Nevertheless, several mapped resources contain reusable components relevant to PATTERN priorities—such as Open Access, FAIR data, and Research Data Management—and some already appear across multiple training areas. Particularly promising resources include practical guides, discussion-based tools, openly accessible books, curated resource portals, and train-the-trainer MOOCs, which combine content knowledge with didactic guidance.

Overall, while general Open Science and RRI resources are not a focus area, selected materials provide valuable modular content and pedagogical approaches that could be selectively reused or adapted in later stages of the project if needed.